

Trends and Development in Policy Implementation in Nigeria: Fresh Ceramic Graduates any Hope of Survival?

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Abstract:

This study opines that the skills acquired by fresh graduate Ceramists during the period of training in higher institutions should form the basis for setting up small scale ceramic outfits of their own. This conception is to solve the pandemic state of unemployment in Nigeria. The multiplex Socio-economic problems are traceable to the past colonial system of government that introduced new trends and tendencies into the African lives, without giving adequate room for adjustment, by the introduction of white collar jobs. This paper attempts to suggest ways of reversing the trend to an employment generating one, by the involvement of fresh ceramic graduates from the nation's higher institutions of learning for entrepreneurial competencies in order to boost the private sector participation in the economy. Theoretical frame work was explored to seek avenue for such graduates to map out professional prospects for themselves. In addition, the paper also made Suggestions for proactive participation of government and its agencies working closely with professional bodies like the Ceramics Association of Nigeria (CerAN) and other similar bodies in the development of pottery and ceramic sector of the economy.

Introduction Nigeria as a country occupies strategic position economically and politically in the West African sub-region, the African region and the world as a whole. Its foreign policy had always centered on Africa, hence it is generally referred to as Giant of Africa by other African states. Ironically, in recent times, due to its slow pace of internal development and poor policy implementation, despite abundant human and material resources at her disposal seems to have assumed the status of sleeping Giant. If this trend is not checked it may further hinder the wheel of progress; whereas the high expectation of the twenty-first century may be unattainable in view of the United Nations general assembly mandate for the World, the Millennium Development Goal' in the year 2000 in which Nigeria was a signatory and the Vision 2020 in which the citizenry expect some lease of life. Interestingly on attainment of independence in 1960 it had provide the needed leadership and support to several African states. The vacation of the colonial regime ushered in self-rule on independence in 1960, it became imperative for indigenes to fill vacant post created by the exit of their White Masters. This made the civil service a major employer of labour, coupled with oil boom era of the seventies was such that fresh graduate from the nation's Universities prefers white collar jobs. Sadly

, this trend had continued unabated into the new millennium, resulting into massive state of unemployment which can best be described as pandemic.

Oyeyinka, (2001) in enumerating efforts of various regimes at promoting Small and Medium Enterprise in Nigeria elicit that "according to the new industrial policy, the government states that the 'Small and Medium Enterprise' (SMEs) form the nucleus of industrialization... that given the

structure of the industrial sector, SMEs, hold the greatest prospect for growth." This policy was to avert the recession that retarded blossoming in the economy resulting from past policy failures. In addressing industrial problems in Nigeria, different regimes had put in place numerous bodies or agencies among which are the Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND), the Nigerian Industrial Development Bank (NIDB), the Small and Medium Industries Development Agency (SMIDA) and several others which go to show that government actually mean well to put in place pragmatic economic reforms for Nigerians. Although, Okunna (2006) worries that "these bodies and agencies still need to be better known in terms of what they can do statutorily for graduates who want to set up their own enterprise." The ceramics graduates, going by their training possess the mental and technical capabilities to engage the economy positively, what this researcher is querying is the will and drives due to bureaucratic arrangement of government and its agencies, as this seems to be causing some forms of frustrations in the economy which is slowly grinding to a halt.

The numerous bureaucratic bottle necks in government policies could hamper the progress of fresh ceramic graduates in job creation and employment generation. Partial or complete eradication of the existing bottle necks in policy implementation may bring about a reversal in the ugly trend of white collar job syndrome prevalent in Nigeria among fresh Universities graduates in general and ceramic graduates in particular. This therefore, calls for multi-dimensional ways in redirecting the higher educational systems, a re-orientation of students' attitudes to the concepts of theory and practice. In a study carried out by Oyeyinka on 'Inter-Firm Linkage, Cluster Dynamism and Market Demand,' the study reveals that "in broad terms, there are several forms of inter-firm linkages in both developed and developing countries among which are: subcontracting, market linkage with customers and suppliers, informal and formal collaborations (joint ventures, franchise), membership of professional and

trade associations and movement of skilled staff from one firm to another." Inter-firm linkages, cluster based on specialization in view of the large Nigerian market combined with the West-African sub-regional market is the focal theory upon which this paper is footed. The paper will therefore attempt to focus on the dynamism of the Small Scale Enterprise (SMEs) sector, as a model for the Survival of 'Fresh Graduate Ceramists in the area and employment generations. Okunna (2009) reveals that "... equipped through training the ceramist is position to benefit from ceramics for the enormous capacity it has for employment generation and thus be able to walk away from poverty." This will no doubt absorb considerable number of the teeming unemployed Nigerian youths in the field of issues raised in this discusses anything to go by, there should be a proactive participation of government and its agencies in the development of the private sector of the economy.

Graduate Entrepreneurship

In charting a way forward, in the opinion of this study, the skills acquired by fresh graduates during the period of training in the higher institutions should form the basis for the setting up of small scale ceramic outfits as an avenue to fully explore career possibilities in ceramic productions. This paper wishes to reinstate the pronouncement of Okunna, (2006) that government policies which established the National Directorate of Employment (NDE), NAPEP (National Poverty Eradication Programme) the NEEDS (National Economic Empowerment strategy) have not been felt in practical term. That is why this paper is in support of a more proactive participation of government, by engaging in laudable result-oriented programmes. Dayo, (2009) states that "the Federal Government has recognized the need to strategically industrialize Nigeria, if she is to maintain her position as the "Giant of African." In line with this, the Vision 2010 committee was set up to assess various issues concerning the global development of Nigeria." In evaluating the Vision 2010 committee's report which covers wide range of issues pertaining to the state of the economy, as commendable. This highlights several issues a few of which suggests the increased participation of the

private sector and a reduction of the Public sector dominance in the economy, also advocating a strong partnership between the public and the private sectors in order to develop a strong economy that is private sector driven.

In view of the above policy statements, the present circumstance in Nigeria seems harsh, isolated from the theoretical frame work of government policies enumerated in the various Agencies mandates. As this study observed in most states of the federation, high tax regime and insensitive posture of some state governments to the plight private sector development seems to scare ceramics graduates from the Nation's higher Institutions from engaging in private practice as a means of livelihood and employment generation; rather, what is obtained after graduation is that they swell the numbers of unemployed youths seeking for ready-made jobs popularly styled 'white collar jobs' that are nonexistent. In a pilot study conducted in 2008 covering Edo and Delta States, the study centred on respondent with NCES, Diplomas, Bachelors, Masters and PhD holders in ceramics using random sampling open-ended interviews to arrive at the summary where the survey population was 125 (See figures 1) to determine the spatial employment spread in both states. It was however found out after analysis of the result collected that the ceramists who reside in these two states were mostly engaged in teaching at the secondary schools, colleges of education, polytechnics, and Universities. Some were employed in government Sub-ministries, Ministries, and Armed forces; with greater numbers also employed in the Private sector, rendering services in banks, advertising firms, breweries, television stations and several other outfits in the two states. The last category (others) in the groups were the unemployed who were idle for reasons due to lack of take-off capital, while in the same group some choose to return to school to further their studies just to occupy themselves.

The objective of the survey was to identify the policy issue that needed to be tackled to reverse the problem of non participation of ceramics graduates in small scale

entrepreneurship sub sector of the economy The outcome of the survey shows that they were engaged in services totally different from what they were initially trained for. In a nutshell, the entire respondent strongly agreed that government should provide them with some sort of soft landing at graduation to practice what they were trained for. The national issue begging for answer is, will government ever commence implementation of its laudable policies? Ada (2006) posits that "Ceramics being a practically oriented profession and relates directly to the file of the people and encourages as well as promotes economic growth in the society." Ceramics business like most human economic activities are predicated on proper funding focused national economic policies that are motivating and guarantees trust for private investors' participation in the economy. There are several directions fresh graduate ceramists may explore in raising fund going by Oyeyinka, (2001, web document) which highlights primary source of funding among others as "family ties, spatial proximity, friends, or former colleagues from courses or work and social networks as factors that may foster informal relationship and collaboration for business take-off." This option has its own setback in view of the existing harsh economic environment in the country. The professional training given to ceramics graduates in institutions of higher learning has the capacity to prepare them in various specialized areas, as Studio Artist potter ceramic equipment engineering/fabrication, industrial ceramics production/services: architectural ceramics; ceramics raw material exploration; processing and packaging of ceramics raw materials ceramics art sales and promotions the lists are endless. The non-implementation of reduction of imposed cost of doing business in Nigeria, and the lack of government active promotion of competition by deregulating and liberalizing the economy seems to be hampering ceramics development and survival.

Recommendations:

There is no doubt that past and immediate administrations had demonstrated their intentions to improve the economy by their

Numerous policies on economic development blue prints. To mention a few, such as National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), Vision 2010 committee's report in 1996, hampering on reviving the economy. The National Poverty Alleviation Programme (NAPEP) in 2001, which was set up to monitor four other schemes; Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES), Rural Infrastructure Development Scheme (RIDS), Social Welfare Services Scheme (SOWESS) and Natural Resources Development and Conservation Scheme (NRDCS). What is indeed lacking is commitment to successful implementation of the numerous government policies contained in each of its agencies mandates. Although, these various policies are good concept on paper, but in practical terms, it had not met the yearnings and aspirations of Nigerians.

This study wish to lend credence to the opinions of several eminent scholars that government must be more proactive in the implementation of its programmes and policies. The situation where industries are ailing due to instability in government policies needs to be addressed head-on to boost confidence of investors thereby encouraging more participation in the private sector of the economy. The government needs to protect its local industries from super foreign industries that often flood the Nigerian market with their goods at a cheaper price to the detriment of our national industrial growth. There is urgent need of removal of existing limitations which had hampered local industrial growth and putting in place a structure that will be more industrially friendly than what it is presently. This paper wishes to canvass that the one year for the national service is converted to an intensive induction in entrepreneurship for practical based courses of which ceramics is included and fund made available to participants on completion of the program. The long term benefit this would have on the young graduates in entrepreneurship development will result to higher propensity for job creation and employment generation in the economy. Government should put in place an industrial intervention fund which

will be made available to fresh graduate ceramists through their institutions of learning at graduation while using their certificates as the only means of collateral. The issue of epileptic power generation and the rising cost of fuel need to be critically reviewed as these are important indices for industrial development. Additionally, there is urgent need for government and its agencies working closely with professional bodies like the Ceramics Association of Nigeria (Ceran) and other similar bodies in the development of pottery and ceramic sector of the economy.

Conclusion

The education of ceramics graduates in the nation's higher institutions has the capacity for wealth creation, employment generation and poverty reduction in line with Vision 2020 aspiration. The demand for industrial and house-hold ceramics in Nigeria can be catered for locally so long as government creates the enabling conditions for entrepreneurs to thrive. Nigeria is a country endowed with human and natural resources, if properly managed have the capacity to develop ceramics industry to meet not only the demand of the Nigerian market but that of the West African regional market. There are enough policies developed by numerous committees which have good programmes with specific target time that often has its goal post shifted; there had been vision for 2010 which was not realized, now it is vision for 2020 orchestrated by the present regime. Therefore, there is an urgent need for appraisal of trends that led to past policies failures in order to turn the economy around to guarantee the survival of fresh ceramics graduates now and the future.

Fig: 1. Exploded Pie Chart Summary of Percentage Spread of Ceramists in Edo and Delta states; N=125Source:Eweka, K.J. survey 2008.

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